

Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for
High Performance Bioseparations

FUTURE
EXPLOITATION

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Add creator of Collaborative Network: José Dinis, Petra Albuquerque

Add contributor(s) of Collaborative Model: Paula Urze, Fernanda Llussá

Add creator of Business Plan: Fernanda Llussá

Add contributor(s) of Business Plan: Cristina Peixoto, André Nascimento, José Dinis

Final revision: Bárbara Diogo, Cecília Roque

Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Acronym	
NOVA-FCT	Nova School of Science and Technology
iBET	Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica
VLP	Virus-like particles

1. Introduction

This document is structured into two distinct yet interconnected sections, focusing on key aspects of future exploitation strategies. In the first part, we explore the concept of a collaborative network model, which emphasizes the importance of collaboration among various stakeholders to drive innovation.

In the second part, a business plan is presented, detailing a strategy for transferring PURE technology to the market. This plan serves as a guide for stakeholders, to understand the PURE project, its market potential, value proposition, as well as the key drivers and barriers involved in ensuring its successful market transfer.

Together, these two sections aim to provide an approach to PURE's future exploitation, blending innovative collaboration with business planning.

2. Collaborative Network: A Theoretical Perspective

In science, research is conducted by groups, assessed by peer reviews and built upon collaborations. Collaborative efforts generally lead to most productive, creative, and innovative results. Hence, experts and actors from diverse backgrounds organize themselves into collaborative networks, composed of autonomous, geographically distributed and transdisciplinary components, which are drivers of value creation. Collaborative networks are dynamic structures governed by the emergence of the process and interpersonal relations by exchanging ideas, resources, trust and lead to innovation.

Typically, a collaborative network is formed for the research and development of an innovative idea, new methodology or product. Therefore, there are four distinct approaches to assemble a collaborative network:

First, formal collaborative networks use past projects successful experiences, taking advantage of members' previous experiences where they collaborate exclusively within their own network. However, the second approach, informal collaborative networks, involves the use of outside channels to construct its network, such as online tools, social media channels or mailing lists. It is reported that the latter approach can augment the possibility of integrating members with greater expertise and that they require coordinators who know well the networks of the network members. The third approach involves networking events, typically organized adjacent to a scientific conference or as standalone events. These events are organized in a way when specific funding opportunities are open, this allows participants to seek collaborations that add specific expertise currently outside existing collaborative networks. Finally, the fourth approach for constructing collaborative networks allows a broader display of expertise, using online tools.

Considering these theoretical aspects of a collaborative network, it is intended to design a preliminary collaborative model of PURE where several components regarding the nature of its network are going to be addressed, such as: background and expertise of the PURE Members, to characterize the actors in this project regarding their industry or academic backgrounds, as well as their main field of study; the applied and fundamental research

components of the project and how it reflects in terms of the research process in the project, the external relationships (particularly with industry), and the dissemination drivers most relevant to the diffusion of the knowledge produced within the project; transdisciplinarity and how the diversity of disciplines and backgrounds in the project interact to produce a knowledge in context of application with social implications; and finally, how trust influences the relationships and knowledge production within the project. Therefore, a qualitative approach was taken in the form of semi-structured interviews, whose methodology will be explained in the next section.

2.1. Methodology

This research work has the main objective of studying the research and development within the context of PURE Technology and its future exploitation. In addition, this work also lays out criteria for the development of a collaborative framework model for European FET-OPEN Projects using this consortium as baseline.

This empirical work was based mainly on semi-structured interviews (that obey to a script). The interviews were divided in two sets. First, six members of the PURE Consortium were interviewed based on their role in the project, background, and their institution. Seniority and institution diversity were both prioritized. The interviews took place during conducted during January and February 2022. The interviews took approximately 360 minutes in total (1 hour per interview), they were recorded upon consent and transcribed with Otter.ai software. A pilot interview was conducted to review the script and to select the topics and the questions that were the most relevant. All the information related to the interview is described in Table I.

Table.I – Interviewee identification by institution. Interview information by date and duration in minutes.

<i>Interviewee</i>	<i>Interview Date</i>	<i>Duration (min)</i>
Interviewee A	27/01/2022	55
Interviewee B	25/01/2022	70
Interviewee C	31/01/2022	77
Interviewee D	31/01/2022	47
Interviewee E	14/02/2022	48
Interviewee F	17/01/2022	92
Interviewee AB 1	04/05/2022	58
Interviewee AB 2	06/05/2022	48

The interviews were divided in six sections. First, the Prior Knowledge section focuses on interviewees’ professional and academic background, European Project management/participation experience and their role within the project. The second section was knowledge production and transference with the focus on applied and fundamental, as well as how interviewees view the share of knowledge with industry. Third, this section

explores the transdisciplinarity strand in the project, specifying the how it can influence the research path and innovation opportunities, as well as be a barrier to the advancement of the project's goals. Next, the fourth section focuses on trust and communication between the project's members and the industry actors that have a peer review role within the project, namely the Advisory Board. These are all fundamental components of the collaborative framework model being designed. The fifth and sixth sections are part of the technology market transfer strategy and intended to assess the inventors' take on the PURE Technology's value proposition and attributes, as well as potential applications for further exploitation purposes and helped with the Business Plan.

The second set of interviews were market research oriented and served as the primary data of the business plan section of this work. The interviewees were four members from the Advisory Board of the project, with academic and industry experience. The length of the interviews was approximately thirty minutes and were conducted during May 2022. The topics of the interviews consisted in six questions on the stakeholder's know-how and expertise, the project's value proposition, attributes, possible the barriers of implementation of this technology as well as sustainability parameters.

The data analysis of the interviews conducted was based on content analysis methods. The topics of the interviews were divided into codes and subcodes, each one corresponding to the segments of the transcribed interviews (Table 2). All data was processed and analysed using MaxQDA Pro 2022.

Table 2. - Interview categories, subcategories, and indicators.

Categories	Subcategories	Indicators
Background	Career path	Expertise Past Projects
	Current role	Role in the consortium
Applied and fundamental research	In the project	Both Fundamental research
	Throughout career	Applied research
Knowledge transfer	Relationships	External relationships Internal relationships PhD students in industry Papers
	Drivers for knowledge transfer	Conferences Meetings
Transdisciplinarity	Transdisciplinary environment	
	Communication	
Trust	Trust inside the consortium	
	Trust outside the consortium	

In Table 2, the codes resulting from the interview analysis obtained by MaxQDA Pro 2022 are represented. The method of data analysis followed in this study was Interviewee to the organization and division of the data into categories, subcategories, and indicators. The categories in this study were respective to the main topics of the interview, which amounted to five different categories (Background, Applied and fundamental research, Knowledge Transfer, Transdisciplinarity and Trust).

During the content analysis of the interviews, the segmentation of the knowledge took place due to the variety of themes within each category covered. Therefore, several subcategories were created to classify the content in a more effective way. Each subcategory, however, may also demand a deeper specificity in that topic, which required the creation of indicators which add another layer to this analysis. In the next section, the results of the interviews will be discussed within the framework of content analysis previously explained.

2.2. Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of the qualitative semi-structured interviews will be discussed related to PURE consortium and the functioning of the collaborative network. However, only the first four sections of the interviews will be presented in this session because they are related to PURE consortium functioning (the others are related to business plan).

Background and expertise

In this first section, the background and expertise of PURE Members was assessed to give a deep understanding and context of the actors who take part in this project. In this interviews, all members' names were pseudonymised and will be referred to with their code names according to EU Data Protection and a consent form was signed. Most of the interviewees have large experience participating in consortium networks and have already been coordinators in some projects. Most of them has extensive industry networks or constant contact with industry. However, only one has worked in industry. Moreover, most of the participants stated that the main difference from academia and industry is the deadlines imposed, where in academia there are much looser deadlines than in industry. In addition, in a European Project like PURE it is of utmost importance the compliance with deadlines since this is the rules adopted by the FET-OPEN project framework.

Therefore, in the next section the fusion of applied and fundamental research methodologies will be addressed since to assess how industry-like methodologies and rules coexist with a mainly academic research project.

Applied or Fundamental Research

In this section, the research aims to verify if this consortium follows the Mode 2 Production of Knowledge criteria of knowledge produced in context of application, given that this project, as stated before, has the main goal of application and, therefore, implies the fusion and collaboration with industry practices and methodologies. Therefore, three subcategories were studied: first, the methodology practiced by each interviewee in their careers and in the PURE Consortium; then, it was asked what are the most relevant drivers for transferring the

knowledge produced in the project to industry stakeholders; and finally, the last subcategory intended to study the relationships in the project between the core members and the Advisory Board, the peer-review body in the project that provides the more direct connection with industry.

Type of research methodology in PURE

PURE Members' background is mainly academic; therefore, it was expected that their experience would be mostly with fundamental research. However, since they have some sort of contact with industry it was poignant to investigate what the patterns of research methodology were throughout PURE Members' careers, and how they translate to the methodology of the project.

Interviewee A has stated that he has expertise in translating materials for bioseparation into practice, which can be classified as applied research experience throughout his career. Therefore, he perceives fundamental research as the cornerstone of PURE, stating that "PURE has a very strong element of fundamental research. It is rooted in the project." In addition, he also affirms that applied and fundamental research are equally important in the project, and that they are not so easily distinguished. Although, he believes that applied research only should be thought about if the fundamental research problems can be solved.

In the case of Interviewee B, she has been more applied oriented since the beginning of her career, as evidenced by the quote "Even in my PhD I did more applied research." This interviewee has had experience working in industry which reveals the applied focus, but also within her career in academia today, Interviewee B is preoccupied in merging the two types of research together. Regarding the PURE Project, similarly as Interviewee A, Interviewee B states that the focus now should be first in the proof-of-concept that the project proposed, which is achieving the "(...) precise modification of the adsorbents (...)", and then as soon as the fundamental research is completed, then the project should focus on the performance for the application of the adsorbents.

On the other hand, Interviewee C has worked most of her career in a company that combines fundamental research with applied research, highlighting that she has experience on both ends "(...) I have done fundamental research for application." Furthermore, she also asserts that her own research has been transferred to patents that, nowadays, are being used by a company. Additionally, Interviewee C is also of the opinion that the project, at the time in which interviews were conducted, the fundamental research should be the focus because of the novelty of the application. However, once again, a key element of Mode 2 Production of Knowledge is evidenced when Interviewee C mentions that even though the project is developing fundamental research, the focus should be application ("I think you can only do the best out of everything to pursue an application. Anything that is done in our group is fundamental research, but we always have a focus on application.").

Next, Interviewee D, made the distinction between her institution and the other institutions in the project, enforcing that her institution is "(...) more applied oriented" and all the other partners are "(...) really strong in fundamental research". This statement adds on to the general notion that the project consists of a fusion between fundamental and research elements, in which one complements the other by having an institution responsible for the

application and the scalability of the technology being developed at the fundamental stage. Moreover, this thesis is sustained because Interviewee D also believes that fundamental science is essential for the development of any application and that fundamental and applied research are difficult to distinguish.

Interviewee E, in similarity to the other interviewees, states that both fundamental and applied research are equally important to the project. On one hand, Interviewee E says that “(...) you always need to keep in mind that there is the other end therefore, it helps if you know both ends (...)”, which means that there is a combination of both methodologies for the project at-large to succeed. In addition, Interviewee E notes that the senior members in the consortium have great experience with both methodologies, attributing this as an advantage.

Finally, Interviewee F is of the same opinion as their colleagues that there should be a combination of both methodologies. However, she goes one step forward in asserting that technology design is greatly affected by the fundamental research performed, because if a researcher doesn't comprehend the fundamentals of their research, they will never be able to control their work or predict their system, which will compromise technology development (“(...) Then you start finding out that something is happening as a result, so most of the times you need to do things that you don't know exactly what is going to happen but then if you don't try to understand why this has happened, you will never be able to predict or design your system so you cannot have a technology.”).

Relationships with industry

In this subsection, relationships in the project were studied to give a broader notion on how the project members collaborate with internal and external industry actors. Therefore, we can classify the relationships between members of the project with the Advisory Board as inside the project, whereas with industry are called relationships outside the Project.

First, Interviewee B considers that the proximity of this project to industry is shown in two different fronts. On one hand, she considers that inside the project there is a SME, iBET, that works directly with industrial scale-up of these “(...) supports for bioseparation (...)” and has deep knowledge of the needs of the market. The presence of such company is essential, as evidenced by the quote “(...) we need to have those kinds of people on board.” On the other hand, Interviewee B infers that the Advisory Board is also an asset because they have industry experience with the materials that the Project is working with, which is as an advantage. Interviewee D, also is of the opinion that the Advisory Board and the network of each partner are extremely helpful for expanding and deepening the project's connection with industry.

In the case of Interviewee C, she recognizes that the Advisory Board is a peer advisory body that is constituted by a “(...) nice mixture of people and even the academic partners have close ties to industry.” Furthermore, Interviewee C also considers that the role of this body is more than consulting on technical and market issues. She also perceives them as being a key knowledge transfer drivers and vehicles of dissemination of the project's results and vision (“It happens very often that they talk to each other and get to know things from each other, so it is good to have company partners in this project not only in the advisory board”). This way, the project gains notoriety and credibility because valued members in industry and academia spread the word on their work. However, the relationship with these industry stakeholders can hit roadblocks, because the companies that are involved can be considered

competitors, so this issue has to be resolved in the form of technology licensing and IP Protection, as it was illustrated by Interviewee C's own personal experience ("I sold methods and licensing which is not all patents because we cannot afford it, so we sell the patents to company partners meaning they keep the materials or the knowledge secrets that we produce."). Finally, it was also noted that the relationship with industry in PURE is satisfactory, however this interviewee believes the project should invest more in expanding its industry network "I think we have a very good connection to industry, but I think there should be more." The approximation to industry should only be done as soon as the project's proof-of-concept is proved and that there are opportunities for commercialization.

Ultimately, Interviewee F affirms that the Advisory Board is the Project's closest relationship with industry ("Our closest relationship in the industry is really in the advisory board (...)", alongside with the connections from the project's members own professional networks network. However, these relationships are a way to complement a lack of presence of an industrial partner in the project, which was similarly referred by Interviewee C. The SME present in this project is viewed as "(...) providers of services to industries and customers so it means that in reality in this project we don't really have a company that is an industrial producer."

The connections between the consortium and industry are mainly built around the members' connections and network with the industry. In addition, the Advisory Board is the main reflection of the members' connections given that this body was assembled via previous relationships established.

However, there is a need for the establishment of new connections to expand the PURE's industry network, even though the project is not at the industry scale-up phase. Therefore, in the next subsection some dissemination and knowledge transfer strategies are going to be discussed.

Dissemination drivers and strategies

The dissemination and knowledge exchange must consider the evolution path of technology development. As such, this path is as follows: first, there is early stage invention, where the brainstorming and discussion of possible applications takes place; secondly, the proof of concept where fundamental research dominates the overall research in project development; then, in third place, the reduction to practice, which is the optimization of the methodology and scaling-up; finally, there is the prototyping, formulation, and compound for the commercialization and transfer to the market of this technology.

The PURE Project aims to reach the proof-of-concept stage. However, it is important to discuss the dissemination of this technology to the industry to spread the word and improve the industry network to aid in the other stages of technology development. Therefore, in literature there are several knowledge dissemination strategies with industry. In this study, there were four mechanisms that stood out from the interviews, and they were: conferences, meetings, PhD students working in industry and publications.

First, Interviewee A considers that the knowledge transfer drivers that are the most important to contact the industry in the consortium are international conferences, meetings, and publications. However, he states that "(...) the maintenance of the website (...)" is also extremely poignant given that these are also means of contact with the industry as they are a way to make project advancements relevant to not only the industry, but also to the public. On the other hand, Interviewee B considers that having experienced people in the Advisory

Board working in companies is sufficient for knowledge transfer (“(...) even in our Advisory Board we have someone who has experience with that by working in a company.”).

Furthermore, Interviewee C, as it was reinforced before, when speaking about consortium-industry relationships, mentions again that having industry partners is beneficial for spreading the word, and to disseminate the knowledge produced in the PURE Consortium. In addition, when speaking about publications, she states that “(...) if you only publish maybe, you don’t address industry so well.” This suggests that publications themselves are important, but they need to be accompanied by other vehicles of dissemination.

On the contrary, Interviewee D gives an opposing opinion to Interviewee C, stating that “(...) my experience is that the scientific manuscripts are the stronger ones.”, also adding that in most cases, stakeholders read a publication about a specific topic and then they contact them to receive consultation on that same topic. As such, there is two contrary views on publications as mechanisms of knowledge transfer. Despite these contrary views, Interviewee D also agrees with Interviewee C that the connections/network of all partners are important and will help with knowledge transfer in this consortium. Interviewee D also adds that conferences are means of dissemination of knowledge of fast impact, a view that is complemented by the opinions of Interviewee F that says that interactions in conferences are good platforms to getting to know your own field and to discuss innovation, ideas and problem solving.

Lastly, Interviewee E is the interviewee with the most different view out of all the other interviewees. First, he doesn’t believe that PhD students working in industry is a driving force for knowledge transfer. All the other interviewees didn’t mention this mechanism, which signals the lack of importance given to this mechanism in this consortium. However, Interviewee E believes that the greatest driver of knowledge transfer is himself, justifying this statement by stating “(...) I have the networks and the company contacts and have also the network in terms of media, press and TV (...)”, meaning that he brings to the consortium multiple assets that can help disseminating knowledge and bring more industry contacts to accelerate the process of knowledge transfer.

In the next Section, transdisciplinarity will be addressed to assess how the knowledge production, the relationships within the consortium and the mechanisms for dissemination above described are affected by the diversity of scientific fields and backgrounds in the PURE Project.

Transdisciplinarity

Transdisciplinarity, as stated before, is often characterized by the inclusion of non-academic stakeholders in the process of knowledge production and into problem-solving approaches that are applied to tangible, real-world problem. Therefore, especially in sciences that directly address societal challenges, transdisciplinary teams should be involved in increasing the diversity of fields of expertise, which stimulates innovation and productivity and can outperform competition. In the case of PURE, since it is a consortium formed in a framework of innovation to develop an application that could impact society, it was necessary to investigate how transdisciplinarity affects the research process in PURE.

In PURE, the members of this consortium are from vastly different areas as previously described, and they are: downstream processing, bioengineering, chemistry, bioinformatics, material sciences, economy, and sociology.

In such a diverse team, the dynamics of collaboration were investigated, which involves the understanding of how actors communicate through multiple areas of knowledge, how innovation is created and the barriers that may exist.

The diversity of PURE's expertise is confirmed by Interviewee C, as is evidenced by the quote "(...) the xx group in the modification of proteins and small molecules, chemistry and bioinformatics which is nice, then we contribute with downstream processing the bioseparation topic which is really in our heart of expertise (...)". Moreover, Interviewee C believes that the diverse expertise in the project gives a synergetic effect since the problem that the project proposed to resolve is being addressed from different angles. This effect is also caused by the presence of social scientists in the project, which in her view, is a new opportunity to have a new perspective on the project applicability since the members of the consortium are all natural scientists, therefore this approach would never have been achieved without having "(...) economists and socio-economists there (...)". Furthermore, there is also a general belief that the integration of different natural sciences enables the combination of two completely different techniques that have never been put together before.

Interviewee D reinforces that complementary backgrounds of the members of the consortium allows the team to tackle the challenges in a faster and easier way. Interviewee E also believes that transdisciplinarity and the diversity of disciplines in this consortium is an advantage towards the commercialization of PURE's technology, reinforcing that "(...) if you have absolutely super experts in one field you will never be successful in creating new and novel products for the market." Furthermore, Interviewee F resumes transdisciplinarity as a competitive advantage of the project.

However, there is one element of collaboration within a transdisciplinary consortium that the members interviewed mentioned as relevant and that is communication. On one hand, Interviewee D believes that due to different visions it is extremely important to communicate among consortium members to coordinate strategies and to follow a common research path. In the case of Interviewee E, he believes that communication between people from different areas must be done at a lower level, meaning that the consortium members must have clear mechanisms to communicate their data for members from other areas to understand. Otherwise, according to Interviewee F, it is difficult to share knowledge and communicate your data and work in a clear way, adding that time is needed for learning how to communicate with a fellow partner.

According to the PURE Members, there are several key aspects that define good communication in the consortium. First, the coordinator is key for the mediation and is responsible for bringing the consortium together as a whole, according to Interviewee A, Interviewee C, and Interviewee D. Moreover, in this consortium, the coordination is doing a good job, since the communication is clear, effective, the deadlines are imposed and there is organization. This leadership fomenta a good environment where everyone respects each other's expertise.

Besides the role of the coordinator, there are other communication aspects to consider. One of them, according to Interviewee A is formal communication in a legal framework that respects authorships to validate future patents and technology licencing. Additionally, Interviewee B mentions that having regular meetings increases communication

ease and leads everyone in the consortium to be aware of the work being done, while also clarifying more specific terms to respective areas (“(...) It is important to have regular meetings and also agree on the meaning of the words that you use, because sometimes the words you use don’t mean the same in all scientific fields.”). Moreover, having meetings between the smaller teams is also important because it helps resolve issues within specific tasks and is better to resolve minor issues (“(...) we also have to have meetings between the smaller teams that are solving specific problems within the different tasks instead of having everyone involved.”).

However, good communication depends greatly on how the consortium members and partners trust each other on a personal level and, more importantly, in a professional level. Since trust is the foundation of any project, it is going to be explored in the next section.

Trust

Trust is one of the most important factors to take into account in collaborative networks. Moreover, it has been stated to improve cooperation, partner satisfaction and reduces conflicts. Therefore, in this project the intention was to investigate how trust impacts the collaboration between partners and external relationships that exist with the industry.

First, to investigate trust inside the project, it was key to understand what the key factors when it comes to trust in the consortium. According to Interviewee A, the two main factors that affect trust are previous professional experiences partners and their reputation. This opinion is shared by Interviewee C, stating that trust is helped by the fact that the majority of the project members’ have worked together, which is also reinforced by respect of the expertise and knowledge of each partners’ fields of science. According to Interviewee B, publication track record is extremely important because not only assures the proficiency that they have in their area, but also their ability to “(...) introduce novelty on the top of their research field (...)”. Moreover, there are other particularities associated with trust observed in these interviews. Interviewee B and Interviewee D affirm that trust is also derived from rapid email response and frequent interactions, within a reasonable time frame, as well as following the project’s rules and deadlines previously established by the project coordination team.

On the other hand, trust outside the Project is also investigated and it can be defined by trust with actors external to the project, more specifically the Advisory Board. Therefore, there is a clear concern about the presence of competitors in this body, stating the NDA signed in the beginning of the project is of high importance given it protects intellectual property, according to Interviewees B and D. Moreover, on the issue of Advisory Board member selection, Interviewee A adds that a key factor should be that the members are not competitors otherwise, it could compromise the project’s advancements and, as Interviewee C clarifies, prevents leaks from happening. However, since the Advisory Board has a high level of importance because of their expertise and experience with market transfer, the PURE Members suggest that more frequent communication would help the Project, as suggested by Interviewee B in the following quote “So, it would be interesting to communicate every 6 months or even every 3 months.”

2.3. Collaborative Model for PURE: A Preliminary Attempt

In the latter section, several parameters were laid out that influence the collaboration between partners in the PURE Project. Of all those parameters, four key elements of collaboration stood out as being extremely important for successful collaboration in this consortium: members, research methodology, dissemination, and trust. In detail, in Figure 1 every parameter is represented.

The first element of the collaborative model is the members that compose this project. Moreover, the research presented in the section above outlined that the actors of this consortium are from diverse backgrounds within the natural sciences (Biomaterial Science, Chemistry, Molecular Biology, Bioengineering) and the exact sciences (Computational Sciences). However, one characteristic that distinguishes this consortium is the presence of Social Sciences (Economy and Sociology) as integrative part of the research conducted, where multi and interdisciplinary research is conducted, since there is collective knowledge being produced within the consortium in all these areas.

In addition, the EU FET-OPEN Project framework demands an innovative and socially conscious research approach, to create policy to affect societal change. Thus, in the PURE Project the technology being developed is in Bioprocessing, which demands an effective laboratory-to-market approach since its goal is to reach industry-scale production. Therefore, an industry mindset and methodology are required. Nonetheless, from Figure 2.1, it is possible to observe that this Project is composed of mainly academic actors who have had limited experience with industry projects. Yet, extensive industry network and European project experience contribute to an application focused consortium, given that they are familiar with the industry process and a SME in the Project who on a day-to day basis contacts with the bioprocess and biopharmaceutical industries give enough industry support to the project, according to most of the interviewees.

As described above, the research process in this project is applied oriented, though these findings suggests that fundamental research plays a significant role in this consortium. Given that natural sciences dominate the knowledge production in this consortium, academic practices must be considered by the actors during the proof-of-concept stage of the project, meaning that the goal of application is always present, but the actual research process maintains according to fundamental research practices. It is concluded then that a fusion of both methodologies is required, since in the first stages of project development fundamental research is dominant and in the last stages applied research is the reigning methodology. In addition, Gibbons' Mode 2 Production of Knowledge Theory applies in this case because the knowledge produce is always in the context of application and involves industry methodologies, notwithstanding the core fundamental aspect of the project.

A third element of the collaborative model represented in Figure 2.1, is dissemination because it evaluates the way the project communicates and translates the knowledge produced to the industry and to society, since it is one of its main objectives. Dissemination in this project, according to these findings relies on four factors: solid relationships, meetings, conferences, and publications. On one hand, relationships with industry are of extreme importance because they enable the spreading of the word and diffusion of the project's ideas. These relationships allow for the opportunity of meetings and the attendance of conferences

to expose the project’s findings, as well as the creation of partnerships with key industry stakeholders. On the other hand, publications are going to be crucial to give a scientific credibility to the project because it is what builds confidence in the scientific community about the validity of the results and the outcome of the PURE Project.

Finally, the fourth key element of the preliminary collaborative model designed in this work is trust. Trust is the foundation of collaboration because it enables for the actors to have confidence in each other professionally. Respect and reputation-based relationships are essential to build trust and are the backbone in this project, given that this project was built with people that had previous collaborative experience and respect each other’s work. In addition, trust is reflected in PURE by an effective communication lead by strong leadership of the project coordinator.

All in all, it was possible to design a preliminary model of collaboration for PURE that possibly can be applied to other projects within the EU FET-OPEN Project Framework.

Figure 1 – Preliminary collaboration network model for PURE.

3. Final Remarks

After the empirical evidence and the results demonstrated, it is possible to also affirm that PURE fits the narrative of Mode 2 Production of Knowledge Theory, given that, as evidenced there is heterogeneity in background and expertise. Moreover, a collaborative network preliminary model was designed based on the results in this study. The presence of industry in this consortium is reflected in the Advisory Board.

There is a clear need for an approximation to industry that should be done through, according to the findings, international conferences as way to expand the industry network and connections, and publication of findings as soon as possible as a mechanism of giving

credibility to the work while also spreading the word about the project's achievement and goals.

In addition, there is a common and established notion of the project application roots despite the current research status being uniquely fundamental. Despite this, the members are clearly aware of this context and the methodology of research in the project combines both applied and fundamental research as they complement each other, which matches Gibbons' Theory that there is synergy between industry and academic practices in Mode 2.

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3. Business Plan

I. Executive Summary

Petroleum-based polymeric adsorbents are widespread in daily life, but the need for biobased alternatives is urgent due to sustainability concerns. Rising regulations and environmental impacts have driven extensive research into eco-friendly materials to replace these adsorbents in industries like biopharmaceuticals, cosmetics, water filtration, food, and agriculture.

Regarding the purification device demand in the global biopharma market where PURE intends to enter, it is projected to almost double to \$22.55 billion in 2025, growing 14.4% annually in the 2020-2025 period. In 2025, recombinant proteins make up almost a third of the total with a 34.7% share, followed by vaccines with 21.8% and plasma fractionation with 13.1% market share. Monoclonal antibodies represent the majority (70%) of purification demand within the recombinant protein segment.

Regarding competitors, the pharmaceutical adsorbent filtration market is highly consolidated, with the three largest manufacturers commanding 68% which creates a significant entry barrier for new entrants. Also, it is a highly regulated environment, where even process equipment manufacturers must comply with stringent regulatory standards and product protocols.

Two distinct business model strategies are under consideration for future commercialization of PURE: licensing the technology or an university spin-off. The goal is to bring the innovation to market, generate revenue, and build a sustainable business.

PURE's multidisciplinary team brings together, for the first time, a unique blend of academic and industry expertise, positioning the project to effectively transform this vision into a successful reality. In spite of the high qualified team, key risks for the PURE project include technical challenges, as it is currently at the proof-of-concept stage and has not yet been fully developed or tested at scale. Mitigation strategies for the risks include collaborating with research institutions and experts to tackle technical issues. For the market risks, conducting market research to identify and communicate an unique and differentiated value proposition, build a reliable supply chain through partnerships, and invest in R&D and standardize processes to ensure uniformity in the product, while forming partnerships to secure a steady supply of natural resources and maintain consistent quality. The PURE project is still in its early stages, making it premature to provide detailed financial projections.

Business Idea

I.1. The Problem

Polymeric adsorbents produced from petroleum-based feedstocks are ubiquitous in our daily lives. Biobased alternatives are urgently needed in view of sustainability concerns.

The growing regulatory landscape, coupled with heightened concerns over carbon footprints and the environmental impact of conventional technologies, has catalyzed extensive research into sustainable alternatives. This has led to the demand for new, eco-friendly materials capable of replacing petroleum-based polymeric adsorbents across multiple industries, including biopharmaceuticals, cosmetics, water filtration, food, and agriculture.

Moreover, as major blockbuster biologics approach the end of their patent life, there is an increasing demand for novel biopharmaceutical molecules. This shift is driving significant investment in research and development, leading to a rising need for advanced purification filters. Biopharmaceutical companies are seeking purification solutions that enhance innovation, accelerate time-to-market, reduce costs, and improve sustainability and product quality, all of which are critical for maintaining competitive advantage in a rapidly evolving market.

1.2. The Solution

The PURE project aims to address the significant challenges faced by the biopharmaceutical industry in the bioseparation step of compound development and manufacturing. Specifically, it targets issues related to low productivity, high operational costs, and the substantial environmental impact of current purification processes. This innovative approach not only enhances the efficiency of bioseparation but also aligns with the industry's push for more environmentally friendly processes.

1.3. Technology Description

PURE technology consists in the use of adsorbents with high productivity. It is compatible and can be adapted to various biopharmaceutical products, including monoclonal antibodies, virus like particles, enzymes, growth factors, hormones, vaccines, and cell and gene therapeutical drugs. The integration process involves the adaptation of the technology to existing production lines and the optimization of the bioseparation steps to ensure maximum efficiency, productivity and reproducibility.

1.4. Development Stage of PURE Technology

The technology readiness level (TRL) of PURE is currently level 3 where you have proof of concept validation.

1.5. Intellectual Property

The project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program, and any resulting patents or intellectual property will be managed in accordance with EU regulations.

The technology development includes the protection of intellectual property through patents and licensing agreements. The consortium is committed to ensuring that the intellectual property generated from the project is effectively protected and utilized to maximize its impact on the biopharmaceutical industry.

1.6. Technology Future Development

Future enhancements of PURE technology can include further optimization of the adsorbents, the application to other purification holders and the expansion of the range of biological products that can be effectively separated using this technology. Potential future developments include the use of the technology for the purification of new biopharmaceutical products. The project also aims to explore new applications markets for the technology, ensuring a broader impact outside the biopharmaceutical industry.

2. Market Research and Analysis

2.1. Global Pharmaceutical Adsorbent Filtration Market

Purification device demand in the global biopharma market is projected to almost double to \$22.55 billion in 2025, growing 14.4% annually in the 2020-2025 period, with rapid growth supported by increasing R&D investment, rising purification standards as novel therapeutics are introduced into the market, and COVID-19 vaccine and treatment development (Table 1).

Recombinant proteins make up almost a third of the total with a 34.7% share, followed by vaccines with 21.8% and plasma fractionation with 13.1% market share in 2025 (Table 1).

The fastest growth is projected in the smaller segments of cell and gene therapy, which make up 8% and 7% of the total market, respectively. The demand for purification in cell therapy is expected to grow at an annual rate of 21.2% through 2025, while gene therapy (with adenovirus representing 72% of total demand) is projected to grow at 23% annually during the same period. This growth will be driven by increased use in clinical trials and the growing interest in regenerative medicine for chronic disease treatment.

Monoclonal antibodies represent the majority (70%) of purification demand within the recombinant protein segment and are expected to grow faster than other recombinant proteins—at a rate of 17% per year, compared to 12% for other proteins—due to their use in COVID-19 treatments.

Harvest clarification remains the largest purification step, accounting for 26% of total demand, followed by sterile filtration at 24%. Protein A and ion exchange chromatography represent 13% and 15% of total demand, respectively, with both expected to grow at a faster rate than the traditional clarification and sterile filtration processes due to the higher purity and yield achieved through chromatography.

Table 1. Demand for purification devices in the global biopharma market

(In million dollars)

	Total Demand		Market share	CAGR
	2020	2025	(%) 2025	2025/2020
Total Demand	11,486	22,549	-	14,4%
Chemical Pharma	1,279	1,854	8,2%	7,7%
Vaccines	2,560	4,907	21,8%	13,9%
Plasma Fractionation	1,960	2,961	13,1%	8,6%
Recombinant Proteins	3,987	8,231	36,5%	15,6%
Monoclonal Antibodies	2,791	6,124	27,2%	17,0%
Other	1,196	2,107	9,3%	12,0%
Cell Therapy	915	2,388	10,6%	21,1%
Gene Therapy	784	2,208	9,8%	23,0%
Adenovirus	565	1,769	7,8%	25,6%
Lentivirus	220	439	1,9%	14,9%

Source: Report on Global Pharmaceutical Purification Device Market Market Study – confidential and prepared on behalf of 3M (2021)

Millipore is the clear leader supplier (Figure 1), holding at least 25% of the demand in harvest/clarification, sterile filtration, and viral clearance. Other major players include Pall, Sartorius, 3M, and Cytiva, while additional contributors to the market include Alfa Laval, Asahi Kasei, Beckman Coulter, Cobetter, Eaton, Hitachi, MDI, Nanomicro, Parker Hannifin, Shanghai Jinke, Thermo Fisher, Tosoh, and YMC.

In recent years single-use technologies have become more common in biopharmaceutical production compared to traditional purification methods.

Protein A and ion exchange chromatography are not inherently single-use technologies. Traditionally, both are reusable methods used in biopharmaceutical production for protein purification. However, there has been a growing trend toward integrating single-use components, like disposable columns or adsorbents devices, to improve efficiency, reduce contamination risk, and lower costs. So, while these chromatography techniques can be part of single-use systems, the chromatography methods themselves are not exclusively single-use.

In VLP manufacturing, Protein A adsorbents (43%) are used less than columns (57%) but are expected to grow more due to higher efficiency. " Adsorbents reduce total process time by about 25% compared to columns," says the Head of Adsorbents Chromatography R&D at MilliporeSigma (from 3M Market Report).

Figure 1. Main suppliers of purification devices in global pharma market by market Share
(2020 Total Market = \$1.6 billion)

Source: Report on Global Pharmaceutical Purification Device/Equipment Market Study – confidential and prepared on behalf of 3M (2021)

3.2 Market Analysis of Global Pharmaceutical Adsorbents Market

The main drivers and barriers for the growth of global adsorbents market are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Global Pharmaceutical Adsorbent Filtration Market: Drivers and Barriers

Market Drivers:

a) Growth in the Biopharmaceutical Industry

Adsorbent is a key separation method in the biopharmaceutical industry. The global pharmaceutical market is expected to grow at 5% annually from 2020 to 2027, with the Asia-Pacific region leading this growth. The biopharmaceutical sector is set to grow faster than the overall pharmaceutical industry, driving demand for adsorbent filtration, particularly in North America, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific region.

b) Robust Biopharmaceutical Product Pipeline

Biologics have rapidly become a significant product segment for most pharmaceutical companies. According to the Tufts Center for the Study of Drug Development, biotech products accounted for 71% of the revenue generated by the top 10 pharmaceutical products and R&D is needed for the ones that have patents expiring.

c) Patent Cliff

The impending patent expirations of blockbuster drugs, often referred to as the "patent cliff," are compelling pharmaceutical companies to focus on developing new therapeutic options, with biologics emerging as the primary area for research and development. This is expected to drive long-term demand for adsorbent filtration technologies.

d) Rapid Expansion in Generic Pharmaceuticals Production

The generics market is anticipated to experience substantial growth during the forecast period. The anticipated growth in generics production, along with the tightening regulatory environment in the generics sector, is expected to drive an increased demand for adsorbent filtration technologies within the pharmaceutical industry.

e) Expansion in the Adoption of Single-Use Technologies

Biopharmaceutical manufacturing is subject to rigorous regulatory scrutiny, with strict sanitary and quality requirements at every stage of production. This makes the use of traditional manufacturing equipment both complex and cost-intensive.

Single-use technologies provide greater flexibility and cost-effectiveness, making them a highly attractive alternative to conventional systems. Adsorbent chromatography units are integral components of single-use product portfolios. The increasing adoption of single-use technologies is expected to significantly contribute to the growth of the adsorbent filtration market.

Market Barriers:

a) Decreasing R&D Productivity and Budget Constraints

The pharmaceutical industry faces a challenge of declining R&D productivity despite rising global spending. New drug approvals remain stagnant, which limits progress and poses a constraint on the adsorbent filtration market.

b) Cost Constraints

While adsorbent technology is widely utilized in the developed markets of Europe and North America, its adoption remains limited in the Asia-Pacific region and other emerging

pharmaceutical markets. High costs for replacing consumable components make it difficult to gain traction in these price-sensitive regions, slowing market growth.

c) Market Consolidation and Strict Regulation

The pharmaceutical adsorbent market is highly consolidated, with the top three manufacturers holding 68% of the market share. Strict regulations and this market concentration make it difficult for new entrants to break into the sector.

d) Geopolitical Situation

The impact of the United States trade policy barriers announced in 2025 in the biopharmaceutical industry, especially regarding purification devices, will depend on how trade dynamics evolve and how companies adjust to new economic conditions.

3.3 Competitors Analysis

Regarding competitors, Cytiva's HiTrap Fibro PrismA and HiTrap MabSelect dominate the monoclonal antibody purification market. HiTrap Fibro PrismA offers rapid purification but is limited by reusability. HiTrap MabSelect remains a reliable, cost-effective choice for large-scale purification. GORE Protein Capture ProtA provides fast processing suited for high-throughput applications and it is single-use. Sartorius Rapid A Nano competes in process time with HiTrap Fibro PrismA, with scalability and cost-effectiveness influencing its market adoption.

HiTrap Fibro PrismA uses adsorbents-based fibro chromatography for high binding capacity and fast processing. It allows for high flow rates due to convective mass transfer, making purification cycles faster. However, it has limited reusability compared to traditional resin methods. Its advantages include minimal residence time, scalability, and high dynamic binding capacity, but its higher initial cost and limited reusability are drawbacks.

HiTrap MabSelect employs agarose-based resin chromatography with a protein A ligand for efficient monoclonal antibody purification. It operates at moderate flow rates depending on resin compression and column size. This device offers excellent reusability with proper maintenance, making it cost-effective. Its advantages include high specificity, proven reliability, and a good cost-performance ratio. However, compared to adsorbents-based technologies, it has slower processing times and requires longer equilibration and washing steps.

GORE Protein Capture ProtA uses expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (ePTFE) adsorbent chromatography for high binding efficiency and rapid processing. The adsorbent structure enables high flow rates, making it ideal for quick processes. Though typically single-use, it can be optimized for multiple cycles under certain conditions. Its benefits include fast processing, high efficiency, and superior yield. However, its higher material costs and single-use nature may limit its appeal for cost-sensitive applications.

Rapid A Nano is a adsorbent chromatography device based on nanoadsorbents technology, optimized for high-throughput applications. Its convective mass transfer mechanism allows for rapid purification with high flow rates. Primarily single-use, it may have some reusability potential. Its key advantages are fast processing, high yield, and scalability.

However, the high cost of single-use applications and slower industry adoption compared to resin-based technologies could limit its growth.

Finally, **PURE technology** stands out with its use of adsorbents and functionalization with various ligands, offering high efficiency, scalability, and sustainability. It integrates well with existing biopharmaceutical processes, improving efficiency and reducing environmental impact. PURE's versatility across a range of biopharmaceutical products—including monoclonal antibodies, enzymes, vaccines, and cell and gene therapies—makes it highly adaptable.

Technologies like HiTrap Fibro PrismA, HiTrap MabSelect, Protein Capture ProtA and Rapid A Nano offer specific benefits in speed, binding capacity, and efficiency. However, PURE technology provides a comprehensive solution with high efficiency, scalability, sustainability, and versatility, making it a competitive option.

3. Strategy and Marketing

SWOT Analysis

<p style="text-align: center;">Strength</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PURE addresses a very strategic area of healthcare which is the separation of monoclonal antibodies and VLPs. 2. PURE can have several applications in multiple industries, which can open the door for the development of the exploitation of this technology through several markets. 3. PURE technology integrates well with existing biopharmaceutical processes 4. PURE has an exceptional multidisciplinary team from various disciplines, including biology, chemistry, computational modeling, materials science, and bioprocess engineering committed to reach PURE's vision and opportunity space. 5. PURE's team has complementary knowledge of academic and industrial leading experts. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Weakness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technology still under development (TRL =3) 2. Scalability can be challenging 3. Adsorbent biodegradability conditions are unknown. 4. Need of large amount of funding to continue the research.
<p style="text-align: center;">Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Biobased alternatives of polymeric adsorbents are urgently needed in view of sustainability concerns. 3. Growth in biopharmaceutical industry might require new purification devices 4. Robust Biopharmaceutical Product Pipeline needs R&D 5. Patent Cliff and new purification methods might help patentable innovations in biopharma. 6. Rapid Expansion in Generic Pharmaceuticals Production 7. Expansion in the Adoption of Single-Use Technologies 	<p style="text-align: center;">Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The pharmaceutical adsorbent market is highly consolidated, with the three largest manufacturers commanding 68% which creates a significant entry barrier for new entrants. 2. Highly regulated environment, where even process equipment manufacturers must comply with stringent regulatory standards and product protocols. 3. Decreasing R&D Productivity and Budget Constraints of customers. 4. Cost Constraints 5. Geopolitical Situation

Market Segmentation

The global pharmaceutical adsorbent filtration market **segmentation criteria** chosen to characterize potential clients of the device are technology, application and geography:

Technology Segmentation	Application Segmentation	Geographic Segmentation
- Microfiltration	- Protein Purification	- North America
- Ultrafiltration	- Virus Purification	- Europe
- Nanofiltration	- Virus Removal	- Asia-Pacific
- Chromatography	- Cell Therapy	- Rest of the World
	- Clarification	

Target Market and Positioning

PURE technology intends to enter in purification technology market focusing on protein and virus purification and virus removal. Regarding geographic segmentation PURE'S primary market is North America and Europe.

Chromatography is the central technique of downstream processes in the biopharmaceutical industry. Affinity chromatography is the most used purification method once it allows for the separation of a wide number of contaminants in a single process step.

Packed columns are the most common matrices for chromatography as they are established as primary tools for bioseparation. However, it suffers from several problems such as slow flow speed through the column and low capacity, which leads to low process productivity.

In contrast, adsorbent chromatography can overcome the mentioned problem of packing column and minimize it once it is able to generate a higher flow rate, low pressure drops and has higher productivity per unit time. These reported advantages are due to the flow-through pores of the adsorbent allowing the fast transport of the target protein to the correct binding site. In addition, it has been reported that, monoliths, adsorbents, and adsorbents are viable options to conventional chromatography on bead supports, especially for large biomolecules such as DNA, virus, and virus-like particles.

4. Business Model

Two distinct business model strategies are under consideration for future commercialization: licensing the technology or an university spin-off. The business model serves as a strategic framework that outlines how a company generates, captures, and delivers value. In the following analysis of "Value Delivering", we explore how these two strategies differ in terms of their respective business models.

4.1 Value Proposition

The unique attributes include high performance, increased selectivity, and a reduced environmental footprint. The improved flow results in a system where biomolecules are processed more efficiently and in less time. PURE technology enables process intensification, as it allows for a smaller system capable of processing more material. This reduces the volume required for purification, leading to a smaller environmental footprint, particularly through water reduction.

The technology's ability to use a broad range of ligands enhances its flexibility, allowing it to adapt to various targets without compromising selectivity.

PURE technology is designed to positively impact both the environment and the economy. By improving bioseparation efficiency and reducing waste, it promotes more sustainable biopharmaceutical production. Additionally, its scalability and adaptability can lead to cost savings and enhance the competitiveness of biopharmaceutical manufacturers. With that in mind PURE also aims to create new job opportunities and stimulate economic growth within the biopharmaceutical sector.

5.1 Value Capturing

PURE's business model strategy for capturing value and attracting investment focuses on patenting its technology. This approach safeguards the invention, preserving the value created and making it more difficult for competitors to replicate the innovation. The patenting strategy is essential, as it not only draws external investment but also supports successful commercialization and ensures long-term profitability.

4.2 Value Delivering

The value created by PURE technology and captured by patenting can be delivered through technology licensing or through the creation of a university spin-off.

a) Technology licensing

It's important to note that external funding is essential in the life sciences sector due to the high development costs associated with these products. The industry is highly regulated, and the time-to-market is often lengthy. Additionally, marketing and distribution expenses for these products are also significant. Since universities typically lack the resources to commercialize technologies on their own, technology licensing offers a viable alternative to bring these innovations to market.

b) University Spin-Off

A university spin-off can be established to commercialize the knowledge and expertise developed within PURE. The competitive advantage lies in its unique, specialized know-how that is difficult for competitors to replicate, providing the spin-off with a distinctive edge in the marketplace. The spin-off can focus on further developing and commercializing the technology. This involves refining the product, conducting additional research and development, and scaling up operations for market entry.

Biopharmaceutical companies (e.g., Amgen Inc., Abbvie Inc., Bristol-Myers Squibb Company, Eli Lilly and Company, Norvo Nordisk) may develop new products that require different downstream process methods; therefore, they must partner with a tool provider (e.g., 3M, Sartorius, Pall Corporation, GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Thermo Fisher Scientific) to develop and test a new purification method. The created spin-off can participate in this partnership with customers. Finally, the outcome can be sold to the customer either directly through online catalogues or through large distributors.

The spin-off will need to seek funding to support these activities, such as venture capital, grants, or strategic partnerships. As the company grows, it may expand its intellectual property portfolio, enter new markets, or form collaborations with other entities to accelerate growth and innovation.

5 Team

PURE's team gathers, for the first time, complementary knowledge of academic and industrial leading experts. PURE exceptional multidisciplinary team has expertise in various disciplines, including biology, chemistry, computational modeling, materials science, and bioprocess engineering is committed to reach PURE's vision and opportunity space.

6 Sustainability

PURE technology seeks to generate a substantial positive impact on both environmental and economic outcomes by enhancing the efficiency of bioseparation processes and minimizing waste. This advancement contributes to the promotion of more sustainable biopharmaceutical manufacturing practices as already discussed.

7 Risks and Alternatives

Key-risks for the PURE project include technical challenges, as it is currently at the proof-of-concept stage and has not yet been fully developed or tested at scale.

Market risks involve the supply chain must be secure, with no uncertainty regarding how it will evolve over time. Mitigation strategies for the risks include collaborating with research institutions and experts to tackle technical issues.

For the market risks, conducting market research to identify and communicate an unique and differentiated value proposition, build a reliable supply chain through partnerships, and invest in R&D and standardize processes to ensure uniformity in the product, while forming partnerships to secure a steady supply of natural resources and maintain consistent quality.

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